

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the article lies in the fact that the institutional approach allows for the creation of a sustainable and stable financial system, which is especially important in conditions of economic uncertainty and crises. Effective institutions can mitigate the consequences of financial shocks and contribute to recovery, more efficient resource allocation, which in turn can stimulate economic growth. They provide access to financing for businesses and individuals, which is crucial for economic development. In the context of globalization, the institutional approach facilitates international cooperation in financial regulation. This is important for ensuring financial stability at the global level and preventing financial crises that can have transnational consequences.

Thus, the institutional approach to regulating the financial market is relevant and necessary to ensure its stability, transparency, and efficiency, which in turn contributes to sustainable economic development.

Review of Publications

Numerous scholars examined issues related to changes in institutional structures, regulators, and supervisory bodies in the financial sector, which were created under completely different market conditions. Governments are reviewing their institutional structures for financial regulation, and in some countries, significant changes are made to them. States with similar institutional models boast a wealth of experience on issues related to institutional design for developing an optimal regulatory framework, corporate governance by regulators and supervisory bodies, etc.

H. Farrell & A. L. Newman believe that the global financial crisis, the interaction of domestic regulatory systems has significant international implications. According to the authors, a detailed analysis of international market regulation – the processes by which domestic regulatory activities of states and other actors establish effective rules for markets open internationally – is needed [1].

F. Blgen defines the conditions necessary for a regulatory framework capable of ensuring financial stability. Relying on Hyman Minsky's institutional approach to financial instability, the authors believe that in a weak regulatory environment, financial markets naturally generate instability which can develop into systemic crises. To combat such crises, strong supervision under the auspices of government agencies should be established, and an appropriate regulatory system should be developed through an open and democratic decision-making [2].

L. Zingales writes scholars tend to fall into two opposing camps on the issue of regulating financial markets – extreme libertarians, opposing any kind of regulation, and interventionists,

seeing widespread market failures and favoring large-scale intervention. The author advocates “truth in the middle”, emphasizing mandatory disclosure of any information, i.e. he sees publicity as “a means of fighting social and industrial ills” [3].

On the other hand, S. Beji & A. Belhadj show that financial openness has a detrimental effect on financial development, i.e. it is necessary to ensure a safe transition to financial openness, avoiding its harmful side effects [4].

F. Blgen argues that the financial system can be considered as a public utility and financial stability as a public good. According to the authors, providing the latter cannot rely on private market mechanisms such as self-regulation and price incentives. As capitalism develops through more financialized forms, new institutions and regulatory rules must be developed to redefine market boundaries in order to consolidate systemic stability which is the basic condition for continuous and sustainable economic relations in society [5].

It is well known that crises are part of market life; it is impossible to avoid them. The international financial community has to struggle with the main existing problems that make these events quite frequent, costly and risky for international markets and investors.

A. Icard compares two approaches to organizing the international financial system: the institutional approach (concentrates powers in the field of regulation, supervision of financial intermediaries by creating new bodies or redefining the roles of existing institutions) or the multitherapeutic approach (different problems are solved by different specialized bodies already in existence, adapted to the current situation). The author is inclined to “pragmatic multitherapy”, in particular to the creation of the “Financial Stability Forum” as a temporary initiative necessary to respond to immediate challenges while long-term and more ambitious reforms are being prepared [6].

According to M. Siri & Sh. Zhu, the creation of a common EU framework for sustainable finance and a new financial paradigm, which will require enhanced investor protection, contributes to restoring confidence in the financial sector. The authors believe that the EU reform proposals, while admirable, risk oversimplifying a complex problem that cannot be easily solved without considering its practical implications for each category of financial operators in providing different financial services [7].

Thus, the academic problem of the institutional approach to financial market regulation is relevant and lies in the fact that countries have different financial institutions and regulatory systems, which can lead to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in regulation. This creates difficulties for international cooperation and harmonization of regulations. Moreover, institutions can be slow to adapt to rapidly changing economic conditions and technological innovation. This can lead to existing rules and regulations becoming obsolete and ineffective.

Thus, the scientific problem of the institutional approach to financial market regulation is the need to create effective, adaptive and transparent institutions that can cope with modern challenges and risks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In studying the topic of institutional regulation of financial capital market we used publications in peer-reviewed journals in economics and finance, such as Journal of Economic Issues, Review of International Political Economy, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting, Journal of Economics and Finance and others. The literature on the theory of financial regulation, institutional economics and financial markets was also used.

Research methods: analysis of literature, as well as of current laws and regulations related to financial markets in different countries; review of existing studies and theories on the topic; comparison of different regulatory models in different countries or regions.

RESULTS

Problems of institutional regulation of the financial capital market (on the example of the Russian Federation)

At the present stage Russia faces several problems in the institutional regulation of the financial capital market:

1. Insufficient transparency of the market. In Russia it is not always possible to obtain up-to-date information on the state of companies that are traded on the stock exchange, on the quality of securities issued by them and on organized investment funds. This can lead to unjustified decisions and losses for investors.
2. Low level of investment culture of the population. Despite the fact that the Russian financial capital market has existed for quite a long time, the majority of citizens are still not familiar with the principles of market operation, have no investment experience and do not understand how to manage their finances. This creates risks for their own investments and may lead to improper use of savings.
3. Insufficient development of collective investment institutions. Organized investment funds and stock exchanges in Russia are few, and thus, investors cannot diversify their portfolios effectively enough, which reduces profit opportunities and increases investment risks.

4. Imperfect legislation and malfunctions in its enforcement. Some laws and regulations governing the financial capital market in Russia are not always harmonized and do not respond to the challenges and requirements of the modern world. In addition, some institutions responsible for market control and regulation do not always perform effectively, which may also mean negative consequences for investors.

Solving these problems requires efforts not only from the government but also from investors and representatives of the business community. Addressing the issues needs to include improving the availability and quality of information on companies traded on the financial capital market, expanding investment opportunities for the public, developing collective investment institutions, improving legislation and strengthening enforcement mechanisms.

To improve market transparency, it is necessary to introduce new requirements for information disclosure by companies, improve the quality of auditing and ensure that company reports are available to a wide audience. It is also necessary to strengthen controls over the activities of market participants, including traders, brokers and investment consultants.

Increasing the investment culture of the population can be done through educational programs and campaigns aimed to improve the financial literacy of the population. In addition, the issue of subsidizing financial education of citizens could be considered.

Development of collective investment institutions in Russia can be stimulated through creation of new investment instruments, improvement of legislation and creation of conditions for the development of a private pension fund.

To address the problems of insufficient development of legislation and its enforcement, it is necessary to reform and improve legislation in accordance with international standards and requirements. It is also important to improve the efficiency of regulatory and supervisory bodies and ensure their independence from economic and political interests.

In general, successful solution of the problems of institutional regulation of the financial capital market in Russia requires a comprehensive approach and participation of all stakeholders, including the government, investors and representatives of the business community.

Prospects of development and improvement of institutional regulation of the financial capital market

Prospects of development and improvement of institutional regulation of the financial capital market include the following aspects:

1. Development of new regulatory tools: new technology and changing market conditions require such tools for solving modern market problems more effectively. For instance, these could be digital regulatory tools, use of artificial intelligence to analyze market data, etc.

2. Strengthening the role of regulators: as market complexity and risks increase, it is necessary to make regulators more independent from political influences. This will enable better decision-making in the interests of market participants and society as a whole.

3. Development of international cooperation: in the context of market globalization and increasing international capital flows, international cooperation in market regulation is necessary. This will help reduce the risks of competitive inequalities and improve the coordination of measures to ensure the stability of global financial markets.

4. Improving the availability of information: to ensure more efficient market functioning, information on financial instruments, market participants and their activities is to be easily accessible. For instance, it can be realized through the creation of publicly accessible databases or open portals that will contain information on the state of the market and its participants.

5. Strengthening investor protection: market volatility and increased risks require strengthening investor protection and preventing fraudulent activities in the market. It can be achieved through improving legal protection mechanisms, enhancing the qualifications and professional responsibility of market participants, and improving transparency and control over the activities of market participants.

6. Strengthening measures to prevent financial crises: this can be achieved through improving early warning mechanisms of crises, improving the quality of risk assessment in the market and developing measures to encourage market participants to behave responsibly.

7. Development of financial literacy: to ensure the effectiveness of institutional regulation of the market, it is necessary to raise awareness of the basic principles of financial market functioning among the population. This will help prevent mistakes and irrational decision-making on the part of investors and society as a whole.

In general, the prospects for development and improvement of institutional regulation of the financial capital market are associated with the need to adapt to new market conditions, strengthen the protection of market participants rights and of society as a whole, increase transparency and responsibility of market participants, as well as strengthen the role of regulators and international cooperation.

CONCLUSION

Despite the existing challenges, there are prospects for improving the institutional regulation of the financial capital market. In particular, modern technologies and analytical tools, as well as better coordination between different regulators, can lead to more efficient and transparent regulation of the financial capital market. In addition, improved institutional regulation can

promote the development of the financial sector as a whole and increase its contribution to the country's economic growth. However, to successfully improve institutional regulation, numerous factors such as changes in the global economic environment and national economic conditions need to be taken into account. In general, improvement of institutional regulation of the financial capital market in Russia is an important direction for development of the economy and financial system of the country.

Prospects for an institutional approach to financial market regulation look promising due to the fact that by recognizing the inherent fragility of financial markets and focusing on systemic risks, an institutional approach can lead to a more robust regulatory framework that contributes to overall financial stability. Such a proactive approach can help reduce the likelihood of future financial crises.

Notably, supporting open and democratic decision-making promotes stakeholder engagement and inclusion of diverse views in regulation. This inclusiveness can lead to more widely accepted and effective regulations.

In conclusion, an institutional approach to financial market regulation has significant potential to create a more stable, transparent and comprehensible financial system. By focusing on systemic risks, preventive measures and democratic processes, this approach can contribute to a more resilient financial environment that better meets the needs of all stakeholders.

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